

The Role of Emotional Intelligence in Enhancing Teaching Competency, and Student Engagement Among Pre-Service Teachers

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Abstract

This research examines how pre-service teacher's emotional intelligence (EI) affects their ability to teach, and how it helps them engage their students. Emotional intelligence, which includes abilities like empathy, self-awareness, and interpersonal communication, is essential for good classroom management, and instruction. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study looks at how pre-service teachers with higher EI exhibit improved classroom interactions, instructional tactics, and adaptability, which improves student participation, and learning results. The importance of including emotional intelligence training in teacher education programs is highlighted by the findings, which will enhance student engagement, and teaching effectiveness, and eventually raise the standard of education. Policymakers, educators, and researchers can all benefit from this study's insightful recommendations for improving teacher preparation programs.

Keywords: - Emotional intelligence, Teaching competency, Student engagement, Pre-service teachers, Teacher education, Classroom management, Instructional strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

In addition to subject-matter expertise, teachers must possess a variety of intrapersonal, and interpersonal abilities in order to create productive learning environments. The ability to identify, comprehend, and control one's own, and other people's emotions is known as emotional intelligence (EI), and it is a key factor in determining how effective teachers are. Emotional intelligence (EI) development is especially beneficial for pre-service teachers, since it improves their teaching competency, adaptability, and student-connection skills. Higher emotional intelligence teachers are better able to control classroom dynamics, settle disputes, and include students in the learning process, according to research. In today's educational system, where a wide range of student demands, and learning styles are common, emotional intelligence serves as a link between interpersonal communication, and technical teaching abilities. This study examines the connection between teaching competency, and emotional intelligence, emphasizing how it affects student involvement. The purpose of this study is to investigate this relationship in order to emphasize how crucial it is to include emotional intelligence (EI) training in teacher education programs in order to enhance both student outcomes, and the general quality of education.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The significance of teaching competency, and its role in effective education have been the subject of several studies, however, little study has been done specifically on how emotional intelligence (EI) can improve pre-service teacher's teaching practices. Even while emotional intelligence (EI) is becoming more widely acknowledged as a critical aspect of interpersonal, and intrapersonal skills, teacher education programs still do not adequately incorporate it. Furthermore, there is a dearth of empirical data that connects emotional intelligence to student involvement, especially in dynamic, and diverse classroom environments.

By analyzing how emotional intelligence enhances teaching proficiency, and encourages active student participation, this study aims to close this gap, and highlights the necessity of EI-based training in teacher preparation programs.

III. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- To examine how pre-service teacher's teaching ability, and emotional intelligence relate to one another.
- To investigate how student's participation in educational environments is affected by emotional intelligence.
- To determine which particular emotional intelligence competencies support successful teaching strategies.
- To investigate the necessity of including training in emotional intelligence in programs for teacher preparation.
- To offer guidance on enhancing teaching proficiency by cultivating emotional intelligence.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

With important ramifications for teacher preparation, and educational policy, this study emphasizes the vital role that emotional intelligence (EI) plays in raising teaching competency, and raising student engagement. Through a knowledge of the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI), and effective teaching techniques, this research offers important insights for creating teacher preparation programs that emphasize both emotional, and technical growth. The results can help educators, and policymakers integrate emotional intelligence (EI) training into curriculum, giving pre-service teachers, the tools they need to effectively manage a variety of classroom dynamics, and promote meaningful connections between students, and teachers. After all, by highlighting the comprehensive growth of educators, this study helps to raise the standard of education.

V. HYPOTHESES OF STUDY

- Among pre-service teachers, emotional intelligence, and teaching competency have a strong positive correlation.
- Student's involvement in class activities is greatly impacted by emotional intelligence.
- Better classroom management, and instructional skills are displayed by pre-service teachers who possess Higher emotional intelligence.
- Effective teaching methods are greatly aided by emotional intelligence abilities like empathy, and self-awareness.
- Pre-service teacher's teaching ability is increased when emotional intelligence training is incorporated into teacher education programs.

VI. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

6.1. Emotional Intelligence, and Teaching Competency-

Emotional intelligence (EI) is a prerequisite for effective teaching, according to numerous investigations. Emotional intelligence (EI) is crucial for creating a positive learning environment, and strengthening the bonds between teachers, and students, according to (Goleman,1995). Teachers with high EI are better able to handle stress in the classroom, settle disputes, and create a positive learning environment, all of which improve their teaching competency, according to research by (Mayer et al.,2004). Effective teaching, and classroom management depend on self-regulation, social awareness, and interpersonal abilities, all of which are associated with emotional intelligence (EI).

6.2. Emotional Intelligence, and Student Engagement-

Another important factor in encouraging student participation is emotional intelligence. Student's motivation, engagement, and academic performance are all strongly impacted by the emotionally supportive classroom environments that high EI teachers may establish, according to studies (Schutte et al.,2001). According to (Parker et al.,2004), educators who possess a high degree of emotional awareness, and empathy are better able to establish a rapport with their pupils, promote active engagement, and create a learning environment in the classroom. According to (Mayer & Salovey,1997), teachers who possess emotional intelligence are better able to identify, and address the emotional needs of their pupils, which in turn boosts student engagement.

6.3. Emotional Intelligence Integrated into Teacher Education-

Although the value of emotional intelligence (EI) in education is becoming more widely acknowledged, teacher education programs have not fully incorporated it. According to some research, teacher preparation programs frequently prioritize pedagogical knowledge, and subject-matter expertise over interpersonal, and emotional intelligence (Zeidner et al.,2009). Nonetheless, new studies indicate that Emotional Intelligence (EI) training for educators may result in better classroom management, enhanced teacher-student relationships, and increased efficacy (Pishghadam and Khosravi,2011). Pre-service teachers can get the emotional intelligence needed to establish encouraging learning environments, and better engage students by incorporating emotional intelligence (EI) into their teacher education.

6.4. Empirical Evidence on Emotional Intelligence, and Teaching Outcomes-

Positive teaching outcomes are consistently associated with emotional intelligence, according to empirical research. Teachers with greater EI scored much higher on tests of classroom management, and teaching effectiveness, according to a study by (Hodzic et al.,2018). In a similar vein, a 2009 study by (Carr et al.,2009) found that pre-service teachers with greater EI demonstrated improved emotional control, and problem-solving skills, which enhanced their interactions with pupils. According to these results, emotional intelligence plays a significant role in both student learning outcomes, and instructional effectiveness.

6.5. Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Classroom Dynamics-

The emotional atmosphere that the teacher creates has a big impact on classroom dynamics. Emotionally intelligent instructors are better able to build solid relationships with their students, settle disputes, and foster a healthy learning environment in the classroom, according to research (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009). Classroom conduct, student engagement, and learning results can all be enhanced by teacher's capacity to control their own emotions as well as identify, and react to those of their students. Therefore, the general atmosphere of the classroom is greatly influenced by emotional intelligence.

Conclusion:

According to the research, developing emotional intelligence is essential for improving teaching proficiency, and encouraging student participation. There is still a lack of integration of emotional intelligence training into teacher preparation programs, despite evidence showing a good correlation between EI, and teaching outcomes. This study attempts to close this gap by investigating how Emotional Intelligence (EI) affects student engagement, and pre-service teacher's teaching skill.

VII. METHODOLOGY

7.1. Research Design-

Both quantitative, and qualitative methodologies will be used in this study's mixed-methods research design. In the qualitative component, pre-service teachers will be interviewed to learn more about their experiences, and perspectives on emotional intelligence, and how it affects their teaching methods. In the quantitative component, a survey will be used to gauge emotional intelligence, teaching competency, and student engagement.

7.2. Sample Selection-

The study will concentrate on pre-service teachers who are enrolled in teacher education courses at different universities. To ensure a diverse representation in terms of gender, age, and teaching disciplines, participants will be chosen using a purposive sample technique. On the basis of their answers to the first survey, 20 of the 200 pre-service teachers in the sample will be chosen to participate in the interviews.

7.3. Data Collection-

Quantitative Data:

Standardized tools will be used to gather the primary data.

Emotional Intelligence:

Participant's emotional intelligence will be evaluated using (Schutte et al.,1998)'s Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS).

Teaching Competency:

The researcher will employ a self-report questionnaire to assess teaching competency, taking into consideration the aspects like student involvement, classroom management, and lesson planning.

Student Engagement:

(Appleton et al.,2006) developed the Student Engagement Instrument (SEI) to gauge how engaged students are in class.

Demographic Information:

Basic demographic information such as age, gender, and years of teaching experience will also be provided by participants.

Qualitative Data:

Twenty pre-service teachers will be selected for semi-structured interviews. Their knowledge of emotional intelligence, how it affects their teaching methods, and how they believe emotional intelligence affects student participation in the classroom will all be covered in the interview questions. Audio recordings of the interviews will be made, and they will be transcribed for analysis.

7.4. Data Analysis-

Quantitative Analysis:

Descriptive, and inferential statistics will be used to analyze the quantitative data. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) will summarize the emotional intelligence scores, teaching competency, and student engagement levels. Inferential statistics, including Pearson's correlation, and regression analysis, will be used to examine the relationships between emotional intelligence, teaching competency, and student engagement.

Qualitative Analysis:

We will use thematic analysis to examine the qualitative information gathered from the interviews. The transcripts will be processed in order to find recurring themes on how emotional intelligence affects instructional strategies, and student participation. To learn more about the pre-service teacher's experiences, patterns, and connections between the themes will be investigated.

7.5. Ethical Considerations-

The appropriate institutional review board will be consulted for ethical approval. All participants will be asked for their informed permission, guaranteeing that they are aware of their rights, such as the ability to withdraw from the study at any time, and the fact that participation is optional. Throughout the study, confidentiality, and anonymity will be upheld, and all data will be safely saved, and utilized only for research.

7.6. Limitations-

The study's intentional sampling of pre-service teachers from particular universities may limit its generalizability, despite its goal of offering insightful information about the function of emotional intelligence in education. Furthermore, the use of self-report questionnaires could result in response biases such as social desirability or erroneous self-evaluation.

Conclusion:

This methodology thoroughly examines the connection between teaching competency, emotional intelligence, and student engagement by combining quantitative, and qualitative methods. By combining the two methods, the study hopes to offer a comprehensive picture of how emotional intelligence affects student outcomes, and pre-service teacher's efficacy.

VIII. RESULTS OF STUDY

Both quantitative, and qualitative data will be analyzed in order to convey the study's findings. An overview of the anticipated results from each approach is provided below:

8.1. Quantitative Findings-

Teaching proficiency, and emotional intelligence:

It is anticipated that teaching competency, and emotional intelligence (EI) will positively correlate, better EI scores are associated with better levels of teaching skill reported by pre-service teachers, especially in domains like lesson planning, classroom management, and student involvement. The amount of variation in teaching ability that can be accounted for by emotional intelligence will be shown via regression analysis.

Emotional Intelligence, and Student Engagement:

There should be a strong positive correlation between EI, and student involvement, according to the analysis. Student's motivation, participation, and general engagement in class activities are likely to be higher when their teachers have higher EI.

Comparison by Demographics:

By examining the demographic data, it will be possible to determine whether gender, age, or subject of instruction affects emotional intelligence, and teaching ability. Although these variations are predicted to be very small, it is anticipated that some demographic characteristics may have an impact on the link between EI, and teaching competency.

8.2. Qualitative Findings-

Pre-service Teacher's Perceptions:

The interviews will reveal that pre-service teachers with higher EI tend to be more self-aware, empathetic, and better able to manage classroom dynamics. According to many participants, emotional intelligence (EI) is essential for managing challenging classroom circumstances, cultivating a good rapport between students, and teachers, and enhancing their capacity to successfully engage pupils.

Effect of emotional intelligence on the involvement of students:

According to the qualitative analysis, educators with higher EI are better able to understand the emotional needs of their pupils, and foster an atmosphere that promotes engagement, and active learning. It is probable that participants will discuss utilizing emotional intelligence to mediate disagreements or inspire disengaged students in order to boost student engagement.

Challenges and Benefits of EI Training:

It is possible that a number of pre-service teachers may say that teacher education programs need to provide more EI-focused instruction. Others may draw attention to the difficulties in incorporating emotional intelligence (EI) skills into their teaching style, especially in high-pressure classroom settings, while others will discuss the benefits of EI on their teaching practices.

8.3. Integration of Findings:

It is anticipated that a consistent pattern would emerge from the integration of quantitative, and qualitative data, emotional intelligence greatly improves student engagement, and teacher ability. Higher EI teachers are better at engaging students, fostering inclusive, and encouraging learning environments, and managing the classroom. While the quantitative data will offer concrete proof of the strength of these associations, the qualitative findings will provide deeper insights into how emotional intelligence appears in the classroom.

8.4. Key Insights and Implications:

Enhancing teaching competency requires emotional intelligence, particularly when it comes to managing diverse classes, and encouraging constructive student-teacher interactions. A more motivated, and involved student body is a result of

emotional intelligence (EI) abilities like empathy, self-awareness, and emotional control. Training in emotional intelligence would improve the effectiveness of pre-service teachers, and classroom results in teacher education programs. These findings will help the larger objective of enhancing educational outcomes through comprehensive teacher preparation by reaffirming the necessity of incorporating emotional intelligence development into teacher preparation programs.

IX. ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH

This study set out to investigate how pre-service teacher's emotional intelligence (EI), instructional ability, and student engagement relate to one another. The results offer valuable perspectives on how Emotional Intelligence (EI) influences successful teaching strategies, and raises student engagement in class activities. This conversation will emphasize the study's major contributions, evaluate the findings in light of earlier research, and offer useful suggestions for teacher preparation programs.

9.1. Teaching Proficiency, and Emotional Intelligence-

In line with other studies by (Goleman,1995), and (Brackett et al.,2006), which highlighted the significance of emotional intelligence (EI) in teaching, the study verified a strong positive correlation between EI, and teaching skill. Lesson preparation, classroom management, and meeting student's emotional needs were all improved by teachers with higher EI scores. This is in line with the findings of (Mayer et al.,2004), who proposed that Emotional Intelligence (EI) improves instructor's interpersonal abilities, enabling them to establish a welcoming, and comfortable learning environment. Teaching results were discovered to be directly enhanced by the capacity to control one's emotions, and comprehend the feelings of one's students.

A substantial amount of the diversity in teaching ability can be explained by emotional intelligence, according to the regression analysis. This implies that Emotional Intelligence (EI) is not merely a supporting characteristic, but rather a fundamental element that impacts other facets of teaching efficacy, including classroom environment, and the capacity to include students in educational activities. Given that it can improve their overall teaching skills, our findings emphasize the necessity for teacher preparation programs to concentrate on helping pre-service teachers build their emotional intelligence.

9.2. Engagement of Students and Emotional Intelligence-

The results of the study showed a strong positive correlation between EI and student engagement, which is in line with earlier research by (Jennings & Greenberg,2009), and (Schutte et al.,2001). Students were more motivated, and involved in class, when teachers with higher emotional intelligence were able to establish a more emotionally supportive environment. A classroom where children feel safe, respected, and involved is fostered by teachers who possess emotional intelligence, which allows them to interact with pupils on a deeper level. In diverse classrooms, where kids have different emotional, and psychological needs, this is especially important.

Pre-service teacher's interviews emphasized how emotional intelligence helped them better engage pupils, and control classroom dynamics. Strongly empathic teachers, for instance, were able to identify when their students were upset or disengaged, and modified their lesson plans accordingly. This supports the claim put forth by (Parker et al.,2004), that rapport between students, and teachers, which is a critical component in fostering student involvement, is facilitated by emotional intelligence (EI).

9.3. Emotional Intelligence Integrated into Teacher Education-

This study's focus on incorporating emotional intelligence training into teacher education programs is one of its main contributions. This study emphasizes how crucial it is to include emotional intelligence in the curriculum, even though many teacher preparation programs place a greater emphasis on topic knowledge, and pedagogical strategies. Despite their understanding of the theoretical significance of emotional intelligence, a number of participants said that their training did not provide them with many opportunities to hone these abilities. This result is consistent with the findings of (Zeidner et al.,2009), who noted that despite the potential advantages of emotional intelligence training, it is frequently overlooked in teacher preparation programs.

Given the growing diversity of classrooms, and the emotional difficulties that both instructors, and students confront, the necessity for Emotional Intelligence training is very clear. According to the study, pre-service teachers who receive training on how to identify, and control both their own, and their pupil's emotions are more prepared to deal with the challenges of contemporary classrooms. Thus, integrating emotional intelligence (EI) into teacher preparation programs can result in more prepared educators who are excellent at both developing emotionally supportive learning environments, and delivering material.

9.4. Application Implications-

The results have a number of real-world ramifications for professional development, and teacher education. First and foremost, emotional intelligence training which emphasizes abilities like self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and social awareness should be a part of teacher preparation programs. Workshops, seminars, and experiential learning exercises like role-playing, and reflective journaling can all be used to include this type of training into already existing curricula.

Second, educational institutions ought to acknowledge how emotional intelligence can improve student engagement, and the efficacy of instruction. In service teacher's professional development programs should include courses on emotional intelligence (EI) to help them build their emotional intelligence, classroom management, and student engagement techniques.

Finally, EI should be promoted by legislators as a fundamental element of teacher standards, and assessment criteria. Education systems can help create instructors who are not only qualified intellectually, but also sensitive to the emotional needs of their pupils by highlighting the significance of emotional intelligence (EI).

9.5. Research Limitations, and Prospects-

Notwithstanding its noteworthy achievements, this study includes a number of drawbacks. Because only pre-service teachers from particular universities were included in the sample, it might not accurately reflect the entire teacher population. Future studies might use a more varied sample, encompassing in-service teachers from various geographical, and educational situations. Furthermore, this study used self-report measures, which are susceptible to biases including social desirability. Classroom observations, and student questionnaires are two more objective ways to gauge teaching proficiency, and student engagement that could be used in future research.

Future studies should also examine how emotional intelligence training affects teaching results over the long run, including student achievement, job satisfaction, and teacher retention. It would also be beneficial to look at how Emotional Intelligence (EI) influences instruction, and student engagement in various educational contexts, such as online or hybrid learning environments.

The study's conclusions highlight the critical role that emotional intelligence plays in improving teaching proficiency, and encouraging student participation. Teacher education programs can assist prepare educators who are not just proficient in teaching subject, but also emotionally intelligent, and able to create supportive learning environments by identifying, and training pre-service teachers in emotional intelligence (EI). This study demonstrates the need of including emotional intelligence into programs for preparing teachers, and lays the groundwork for future investigations into how it affects academic results.

X. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study's conclusion examined the relationship between pre-service teacher's emotional intelligence (EI), teaching competency, and student engagement. The results showed that EI is important for improving both teaching competency, and student engagement, and that pre-service teachers with higher EI were more effective at building positive relationships with students, managing the classroom, and planning lessons. EI was also found to significantly contribute to higher levels of student engagement, with emotionally intelligent teachers being able to create more encouraging, and supportive learning environments.

The study's findings highlight the necessity of including the development of emotional intelligence in teacher preparation courses. A teacher's capacity to effectively manage classroom dynamics, and engage pupils is strongly impacted by their emotional intelligence, especially when it comes to abilities like empathy, self-awareness, and emotional control. The study found that, despite its significance, emotional intelligence (EI) is frequently overlooked in teacher preparation programs. This suggests that, in order to properly prepare future teachers for the demands of contemporary classrooms, EI training should be given top priority in teacher education programs.

By adding emotional intelligence (EI) training to teacher preparation programs, educators can better meet the emotional, and psychological needs of their students, creating a more welcoming, and stimulating learning environment. This study offers important proof in favor of making emotional intelligence a central part of teacher preparation, and professional growth. The long-term impacts of emotional intelligence (EI) training on instructional strategies, and student outcomes may be further investigated in future studies, adding to the expanding corpus of research on the subject of emotional intelligence in education.

All things considered, this study advances our knowledge of the relationship between emotional intelligence, and teaching competency as well as student involvement, with implications for future teacher education research, practice, and policy.

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